

ПРОФЕСІЙНА ОСВІТА

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Psychological and Pedagogical Principles of Forming the Readiness of Future Officers of the Armed Forces of Ukraine for International Communication in Professional Activity

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***Abstract.** The study addresses the relevance of preparing future officers of the Armed Forces of Ukraine for international communication in professional activity, necessitated by Ukraine's strategic orientation towards NATO integration and their growing participation in multinational military cooperation activities and joint missions. Linguistic and intercultural competence is a crucial prerequisite for modern military officers operating in contemporary peacekeeping and coalition environments, requiring effective communication in English and collaboration with diverse cultural backgrounds.*

***Objective.** The article addresses the psychological and pedagogical foundations of this preparation. Its purpose is to substantiate a system of psychological and pedagogical principles that support the development of future officers' readiness for international communication in the Armed Forces of Ukraine.*

***Methods.** The proposed model of officers' readiness includes four interrelated components: cognitive-linguistic, operational-activity-based, motivational-value, and reflexive-evaluative. Its formation is guided by eight key psychological and*

pedagogical principles: integrativity; systematic and sequential learning; accessibility and attainability; active learning; professional orientation; cultural orientation; realism and experiential learning; and multimodal learning. These principles serve as fundamental guidelines for curriculum design and instructional practice.

Results. *The study has substantiated a system of eight psychological and pedagogical principles for the development of readiness for international communication among future officers of the Armed Forces of Ukraine. Each principle addresses specific pedagogical functions while contributing to the holistic formation of the cognitive-linguistic, operational-activity-based, motivational-value, and reflexive-evaluative components of readiness. These principles ensure an integrated and systematic approach to training, aligning content with learners' capabilities, emphasizing active, professionally and culturally oriented, realistic, and multimodal learning experiences.*

Conclusions. *The substantiated system of principles forms a coherent instructional framework for developing officers' foreign language communicative competence, cultural adaptability, and self-regulatory capacity in multilingual, multinational operational environments. This system aligns with current challenges in Ukrainian military education, including meeting STANAG 6001 standards and integrating NATO training doctrines. Further research should focus on empirical validation and adaptability of the model to other security and defence sector branches.*

Keywords: *readiness for international communication; intercultural competence; foreign language communicative competence; professional training of officers; psychological and pedagogical principles; international communication; military education.*

Психолого-педагогічні принципи формування готовності майбутніх офіцерів Збройних Сил України до міжнародної комунікації у професійній діяльності

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***Анотація.** Дослідження присвячене актуальності підготовки майбутніх офіцерів Збройних Сил України до міжнародної комунікації у професійній діяльності, зумовленій стратегічною орієнтацією України на інтеграцію до НАТО та зростаючою участю ЗСУ в багатонаціональному військовому співробітництві та спільних місіях. Іншомовна та міжкультурна компетентність є вирішальною передумовою для сучасних військових офіцерів, які діють у сучасних миротворчих та коаліційних середовищах, вимагаючи ефективного спілкування англійською мовою та співпраці з представниками різних культурних середовищ.*

***Мета.** У статті висвітлено психолого-педагогічні засади цієї підготовки. Її метою є обґрунтування системи психолого-педагогічних принципів, що підтримують формування готовності майбутніх офіцерів до міжнародної комунікації у Збройних Силах України.*

***Методи.** Запропонована модель готовності офіцерів включає чотири взаємопов'язані компоненти: когнітивно-лінгвістичний, операційно-діяльнісний, мотиваційно-ціннісний та рефлексивно-оцінний. Її формування керується вісьмома ключовими психолого-педагогічними принципами: інтегративності; систематичності та послідовності; доступності та посильності; активного навчання; професійної спрямованості; культурологічної спрямованості; реалістичності та досвідного навчання; та*

мультимодального навчання. Ці принципи слугують фундаментальними настановами для розробки навчальних програм та освітньої практики.

Результати. Дослідження обґрунтувало систему з восьми психолого-педагогічних принципів для формування готовності майбутніх офіцерів Збройних Сил України до міжнародної комунікації. Кожен принцип виконує специфічні педагогічні функції, водночас сприяючи цілісному формуванню когнітивно-лінгвістичного, операційно-діяльнісного, мотиваційно-ціннісного та рефлексивно-оцінного компонентів готовності. Ці принципи забезпечують інтегрований та систематичний підхід до навчання, узгоджуючи зміст навчання з можливостями курсантів, наголошуючи на активному, професійно та культурологічно орієнтованому, реалістичному та мультимодальному досвіді навчання.

Висновки. Обґрунтована система принципів формує цілісну навчальну основу для розвитку комунікативної компетентності офіцерів, їх культурної адаптивності та саморегуляції в багатомовних, багатонаціональних операційних середовищах. Ця система розроблена для відповідності поточним викликам у військовому навчанні України, включаючи необхідність дотримання стандартів STANAG 6001 та інтеграції навчальних доктрин НАТО. Подальші дослідження мають зосередитися на емпіричній валідації та адаптації моделі до інших галузей сектору безпеки та оборони.

Ключові слова: готовність до міжнародної комунікації; іншомовна комунікативна компетентність; міжкультурна компетентність; професійна підготовка офіцерів; психолого-педагогічні принципи; міжнародна комунікація; військова освіта.

1. INTRODUCTION

Problem Statement. Amid global security challenges and Ukraine's intensified NATO integration, international communication (IC) has become a critical professional competence for Armed Forces officers. Effective participation in joint missions, peacekeeping operations, and multinational training requires more than language proficiency. Officers must operate confidently in linguistically and culturally diverse environments, where adaptability and intercultural sensitivity are essential [1].

Strategic documents such as Ukraine's Defence Education Policy [2] and the national Roadmap for Language Training [3] stress the need for STANAG 6001 proficiency and intercultural competence as core components of military professionalism. NATO's DEEP initiative further supports curricular alignment with international standards [4].

Despite these efforts, traditional language instruction remains fragmented and insufficiently aligned with operational demands [5]. Broader psychological and pedagogical foundations for IC readiness – especially regarding motivation, cultural flexibility, and reflexivity – remain underdeveloped. While global models (e.g., Bennett [6], Byram [7], Kolb [8]) offer useful frameworks, they have yet to be adapted to Ukraine's military context [9].

A cohesive system of psychological and pedagogical principles is therefore needed to define and support the formation of IC readiness as an integrated element of officers' professional preparation.

Review of Recent Studies. International research confirms the multidimensional nature of intercultural communication competence (ICC) and the necessity of integrated training in military education. Byram's [7] and Deardorff's [1] models describe ICC as a dynamic system of attitudes, knowledge, and behaviours that culminate in effective intercultural interaction. Bennett's [6] Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity (DMIS) adds a developmental view, highlighting progression from ethnocentric to ethnorelative perspectives.

Military-focused studies reinforce this view. Abbe [10] highlights the operational need for sustained ICC training, while McCloskey et al. [11] and Arado [12] emphasise scenario-based, affectively grounded learning. Innovative approaches include virtual reality [13] and visual learning tools [14]. Bahari's review confirms that cognitive load management is vital for success in technology-enhanced ICC learning [15]. Pedagogical foundations such as Kolb's experiential learning model [8], Knowles's andragogy [16], and Bloom's taxonomy [17] shape learner-centred training strategies. These frameworks inform NATO-aligned instructional systems, including those promoted by DEEP [4].

Ukrainian studies increasingly echo these trends. Grebenyuk introduced the concept of IC readiness in military pedagogy [9]; Kanova analysed training gaps [18]; Skrypnikova linked intercultural flexibility with reflection [5]. Recent research by Duzhyi and Derkach [19] and Yarmolovich [20] evidences practical gaps in language and communication training. Although these studies affirm the relevance of IC training, a structured system linking ICC development to pedagogical principles remains absent. The present study addresses this gap through an integrative approach that defines a coherent set of psychological and pedagogical principles aimed at supporting the development of IC readiness in military education.

Unresolved Aspects of the General Problem. Although the importance of IC readiness is increasingly recognised, current research lacks a coherent system of psychological and pedagogical principles adapted to military education. Existing approaches often treat linguistic, intercultural, and operational elements separately. This study addresses the gap by proposing an integrated framework that links key readiness components with relevant instructional principles, tailored to the needs of Ukrainian Armed Forces officer training. The proposed system reflects current NATO-aligned educational standards and supports the holistic development of IC-related competences. It also provides a practical foundation for designing curricula and training environments focused on multilingual, multicultural operational settings.

The purpose of this article is to substantiate a system of psychological and pedagogical principles that support the development of future officers' readiness for international communication in the Armed Forces of Ukraine. Based on an integrative definition, this readiness is viewed as a dynamic, multidimensional quality comprising four components: cognitive-linguistic, operational-activity-based, motivational-value, and reflexive-evaluative. The article demonstrates how each principle contributes to forming these components within professional military education.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

This study draws upon theories of intercultural communication, military language education, and pedagogical psychology. International communication (IC) competence is viewed as a multidimensional construct comprising knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values. Readiness for IC includes four components: cognitive-linguistic, operational-activity-based, motivational-value, and reflexive-evaluative, each rooted in established frameworks.

Byram's model outlines five domains of ICC [7], while Deardorff's pyramid model frames it as a developmental process [1]. Bennett's DMIS describes the evolution from ethnocentrism to ethnorelativism and underpins motivational and reflective development [6].

Pedagogically, adult learning theory [16], experiential learning [8], and Bloom's taxonomy [17] inform the design of learner-centred, progressive training. These models support the formation of intercultural adaptability and professional communication skills.

Military standards such as STANAG 6001 [21] and NATO's DEEP programme guide curriculum development [4]. Ukrainian scholars have adapted these concepts to the national context [5; 9; 18].

This synthesis of international theory and local adaptation forms the foundation for the system of psychological and pedagogical principles presented in this study.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study applies a conceptual methodology to justify a system of psychological and pedagogical principles for forming officers' readiness for IC in military education. The system builds on an integrative authorial definition of readiness as a multidimensional quality, encompassing four components: cognitive-linguistic, operational-activity-based, motivational-value, and reflexive-evaluative. These were identified through analysis of international competence models [1; 7], military standards [21], and national documents [2; 3].

Principles were selected through a multi-step process: reviewing pedagogical literature [8; 16], assessing their relevance to readiness components, and ensuring coverage of content and process dimensions. The final system comprises eight principles – integrativity; systematicity; accessibility; active learning; professional and cultural orientation; realism; and multimodality – grouped into four pedagogical clusters.

Triangulation of theoretical, normative, and empirical sources – including Ukrainian studies – ensured contextual validity [5; 9; 18]. The structure aligns with NATO educational frameworks [4] and was previously presented for peer validation [22].

This framework offers a coherent model tailored to the professional and intercultural demands of officer training in Ukraine.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Principle of Integrativity

The principle of integrativity underlines the interconnected nature of competencies required for IC in military contexts. It involves the purposeful integration of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values across cognitive, affective, and behavioural domains, ensuring holistic development [9; 18].

Supported by Bloom's taxonomy [17], Kolb's experiential learning [8], and constructivist pedagogy [16; 23], this principle ensures that language training is

interwoven with intercultural and professional content. In Ukrainian officer education, integrative approaches help address the traditional separation of language instruction from operational needs [5; 22]. NATO's DEEP initiative also advocates integration, linking language instruction with leadership, intercultural, and mission-specific skills [4]. Practically, this entails simulations, briefings, and cross-cultural communication tasks that mirror operational demands.

Integrativity supports all four components of IC readiness: cognitive-linguistic (linking language and content), operational-activity (realistic tasks), motivational-value (personal purpose and service), and reflexive-evaluative (critical performance analysis). It also ensures horizontal and vertical alignment across disciplines and stages of training, contributing to coherent, mission-relevant officer preparation.

4.2 Principle of Systematicity and Sequence

This principle ensures that learning progresses from simple to complex, aligning educational content with cadets' developmental needs. In military education, it promotes coherent acquisition of communicative competencies relevant to international settings [17, 24].

Rooted in classical didactics and supported by Bloom's taxonomy, systematic sequencing facilitates gradual development of linguistic, intercultural, and reflective skills. It also enhances retention and transfer, as confirmed by studies on cognitive load and scaffolding [15; 25]. In Ukraine, the lack of systematicity has led to disjointed instruction [26]. Recent reforms guided by STANAG 6001 and the national roadmap aim to standardise and sequence curricula [3].

This principle supports all four components of IC readiness by structuring learning trajectories, enabling progress tracking, and promoting task complexity. It aligns with adult learning and experiential models, helping cadets build operationally relevant and transferable communication skills [8; 16; 27].

4.3 Principle of Accessibility and Attainability

This principle ensures that training content aligns with learners' capabilities and developmental levels while maintaining sufficient challenge to foster growth [16; 24]. In military education, it guarantees that IC training is realistic and manageable for cadets with diverse backgrounds.

Drawing on Vygotsky's zone of proximal development and the concept of instructional scaffolding [25], this principle supports progressive learning. In IC contexts, cadets advance from controlled practice to complex scenarios that integrate language with sociocultural behaviour [15].

Practical implementation includes differentiated instruction, simulations, and task design that increases in complexity while remaining attainable. Research confirms that these approaches improve performance and motivation [14; 28].

In Ukrainian military education, reforms under STANAG 6001 and DEEP [4] promote learner-centred tools such as Moodle and scenario-based training. Empirical findings show higher motivation when tasks are accessible and relevant [5; 19].

This principle supports all four IC readiness components – enhancing comprehension, operational practice, motivation, and learner reflection – thus enabling cadets to build sustainable international communication competence.

4.4 Principle of Active Learning

Active learning emphasises engagement, interaction, and knowledge construction through meaningful activity rather than passive instruction [29]. In IC training, it enables cadets to build language skills, intercultural awareness, and adaptive behaviours via authentic tasks.

The principle is grounded in constructivist and experiential learning theories. Kolb's cycle [8] – experience, reflection, conceptualisation, experimentation – is effective in IC contexts, as is Knowles's andragogy [16], which highlights relevance and participation in adult learning.

In military education, active learning includes simulations, case studies, and collaborative problem-solving. These methods prepare cadets for intercultural uncertainty and operational demands. Czarnecki argues that such approaches are strategic imperatives for developing leadership, tolerance, and flexibility [30].

Ukrainian academies increasingly adopt active strategies. Cadets engage in role-plays, briefings, and mission simulations that improve linguistic fluency and transfer of skills [5; 26]. Research confirms increased motivation and retention [28; 31].

Active learning enhances all components of IC readiness: embedding communication in tasks (cognitive-linguistic), training responses to dynamic conditions (operational-activity), building relevance (motivational-value), and encouraging reflection and self-assessment (reflexive-evaluative).

4.5 Principle of Professional Orientation

This principle ensures that educational content aligns with real-world military tasks, making IC training directly relevant to operational needs. In multinational contexts, it promotes applied learning grounded in mission-based scenarios and authentic communicative formats [5; 18].

The principle is supported by adult learning theory, which stresses relevance and practicality [16], and by experiential learning theory, which promotes context-rich training [8].

In military pedagogy, professional orientation enhances motivation and competence transfer when training reflects doctrinal realities [10].

In Ukraine, this approach is evident in STANAG 6001-aligned curricula and integration of IC into leadership preparation [3; 26]. Cadets develop skills for briefings, negotiations, and reporting, while gaining intercultural confidence and ethical grounding through identity formation [4].

This principle enhances all four components of IC readiness by contextualising language, fostering purpose, and promoting reflection based on operational relevance.

4.6 Principle of Cultural Orientation

Cultural orientation emphasises the integration of cultural awareness, values, and behavioural norms into the training of officers for IC. It reflects the understanding that language proficiency alone is insufficient for effective performance in multinational settings [1; 7].

Grounded in intercultural theory, the principle draws on Bennett's DMIS [6] and Hofstede's cultural dimensions, which explain how communication styles and leadership expectations vary across cultures. Officers must develop respect, empathy, and adaptability – traits vital in diverse operational contexts.

In military education, cultural content is embedded through simulations, case studies, and exposure to international missions. NATO's DEEP [4] and Ukrainian scholars [5; 9; 18] advocate systematic integration of intercultural learning into curricula.

This principle supports all IC readiness components: it links language and cultural meaning (cognitive-linguistic), prepares for interactional complexity (operational-activity), fosters intercultural openness (motivational-value), and promotes reflection on assumptions (reflexive-evaluative).

Cultural orientation also contributes to ethical competence, as officers must mediate cultural differences and build trust in peacekeeping and coalition environments [10]. It transforms IC training into a multidimensional process of intercultural development.

4.7 Principle of Realism and Experiential Learning

This principle stresses the value of authentic, mission-relevant learning that simulates the complexity of IC. According to Kolb [8] and Czarnecki [30], experiential learning through role-plays, briefings, and intercultural scenarios enables cadets to apply language, adapt, and make decisions in realistic conditions.

Grounded in Dewey's and Knowles's adult learning theories, this approach fosters judgment, improvisation, and emotional engagement. Simulation-based

training improves retention and transfer, especially in professional contexts [32]. NATO doctrine encourages realism through “train as you fight,” promoting immersion in communicative, tactical, and ethical tasks [5]. This supports cognitive interoperability – understanding others’ intent and logic – vital in coalition environments [10].

Realism supports all IC readiness components: it embeds language in real tasks (cognitive-linguistic), prepares cadets for complex operations (operational-activity), increases relevance and motivation (motivational-value), and strengthens reflection through post-task analysis (reflexive-evaluative).

Ultimately, this principle ensures that IC training equips officers not just linguistically but operationally and psychologically for diverse multinational missions.

4.8 Principle of Multimodal Learning

Multimodal learning integrates diverse formats – verbal, visual, auditory, kinaesthetic, and digital – to deepen comprehension and engagement. Grounded in dual coding theory, multimedia learning [28], and cognitive load theory [33], this principle promotes retention by combining modalities while managing overload.

In IC training, cadets benefit from interacting with authentic stimuli – videos, simulations, virtual exchanges – that provide exposure to real accents, gestures, and cultural cues [13; 31]. These methods enhance linguistic and intercultural competence.

Ukrainian military institutions increasingly apply multimodal tools such as Moodle, VBS-3, and animated briefings. Studies confirm that such strategies improve motivation, confidence, and real-world transfer [19; 26].

Multimodality strengthens all components of IC readiness: it contextualises input (cognitive-linguistic), replicates operational constraints (operational-activity), supports learner autonomy (motivational-value), and enables reflection through layered stimuli (reflexive-evaluative). It also supports inclusive, differentiated learning aligned with international trends [34].

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

This study has substantiated a system of eight psychological and pedagogical principles for the development of readiness for international communication among future officers of the Armed Forces of Ukraine. Grounded in an integrative definition and a four-component structural model of readiness, these principles reflect the interdisciplinary nature of professional military education, combining insights from intercultural communication theory, adult learning, military pedagogy, and international standards.

Each principle – integrativity; systematic and sequential learning; accessibility and attainability; active learning; professional orientation; cultural orientation; realism and experiential learning; and multimodal learning – addresses specific pedagogical functions while contributing to the holistic formation of all components of readiness. Together, they form a coherent instructional framework for developing officers' communicative competence, cultural adaptability, and self-regulatory capacity in multilingual, multinational operational environments.

The system is designed to align with current challenges in Ukrainian military education, including the need to meet STANAG 6001 standard, integrate NATO training doctrines, and prepare officers for participation in joint missions and intercultural teams. By linking pedagogical principles with functional readiness outcomes, this approach helps ensure the relevance, transferability, and sustainability of communicative competence acquired during officer training.

Further research should focus on the empirical validation of the proposed system through pilot implementation in military academies and its integration into standardised curricula. Experimental studies may assess the effectiveness of principle-based instruction in enhancing performance across IC-related tasks. Additionally, it is advisable to explore the adaptability of the model to other branches of the security and defence sector, such as the National Guard and State Border Guard Service, where IC is equally critical.

Список використаних джерел

1. Deardorff, D. K. (2006). Identification and assessment of intercultural competence as a student outcome of internationalization. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 10(3), 241–266. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315306287002>
2. Ministry of Defence of Ukraine. (2023). *Policy on military education*. https://www.mil.gov.ua/content/education/politika_mou_osvita.pdf
3. Ministry of Defence of Ukraine. (2021). *Roadmap for improving language training in the Armed Forces of Ukraine (2021–2025)*. https://www.mil.gov.ua/content/education/doroznya_karta_2021.pdf
4. NATO Defence Education Enhancement Programme. (2023). *Faculty Development Curriculum Guide*. https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/2023/7/pdf/deep-faculty-development-curriculum-guid.pdf
5. Скрипнікова, В. О. (2023). Розвиток міжкультурної компетентності майбутніх магістрів військового управління у професійній підготовці (Дис. канд. пед. наук). НУОУ імені Івана Черняхівського.
6. Bennett, M. J. (1993). Towards ethnorelativism: A developmental model of intercultural sensitivity. In R. M. Paige (Ed.), *Education for the intercultural experience* (2nd ed., pp. 21–71). Intercultural Press.
7. Byram, M. (1997). *Teaching and assessing intercultural communicative competence*. Multilingual Matters.
8. Kolb, D. A. (2015). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development* (2nd ed.). Pearson.
9. Гребенюк, Л. В. (2020). Формування готовності майбутніх офіцерів Збройних Сил України до професійної взаємодії у міжнародних операціях з підтримання миру і безпеки (Дис. канд. пед. наук). Хмельницький: НАДПСУ ім. Б. Хмельницького.

10. Abbe, A. (2021). Evaluating military cross-cultural training programs. Expeditions with MCUP, Marine Corps University Press. <https://doi.org/10.36304/ExpwMCUP.2021.06>

11. McCloskey, M., Behymer, K., & Papautsky, E. (2021). Developing cross-cultural competence in military personnel: Theory-based training strategies. *Military Psychology*, 33(3), 199–211.

12. Arado, M. S. (2022). Understanding the development of the intercultural sensitivity of personnel in the US Armed Forces (Doctoral dissertation, University of Minnesota). <https://conservancy.umn.edu/items/3cd350fb-bb4f-4d8e-af0e-172ce73489a4>

13. Akdere, M., Acheson, K., & Jiang, Y. (2021). An examination of the effectiveness of virtual reality technology for intercultural competence development. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 82, 109–120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2021.03.009>

14. AlAli, R. M., & Al-Barakat, A. iA. (2023). Role of teacher understanding about instructional visual aids in developing national and international student learning experiences. *Journal of International Students*, 13(4), 331–354. <https://doi.org/10.32674/jis.v13i4.5197>

15. Bahari, A. (2022). Challenges and affordances of cognitive load management in technology-assisted language learning: A systematic review. *International Journal of Human–Computer Interaction*, 38(1), 85–100. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2021.2019957>

16. Knowles, M. S., Holton, E. F., & Swanson, R. A. (2015). *The adult learner: The definitive classic in adult education and human resource development* (8th ed.). Routledge.

17. Anderson, L. W., & Krathwohl, D. R. (Eds.). (2001). *A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing: A revision of Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives*. Longman.

18. Канова, Л. П. (2024). *Теоретичні та методичні засади професійної іншомовної підготовки офіцерів ЗСУ за стандартами НАТО* [Дис. д-ра пед. наук, Український державний університет імені Михайла Драгоманова]. <http://enpuir.npu.edu.ua/handle/123456789/47586>
19. Duzhyi, R. V., & Derkach, T. M. (2024). Learning styles of the Armed Forces of Ukraine personnel undergoing English language courses. *Educational Technology Quarterly*, 2024(1), 97–119. <https://doi.org/10.55056/etq.659>
20. Yarmolovich, O. I. (2022). Preparation of cadets of higher military educational institutions in Ukraine for perception of professional vocabulary in English classes. *Journal of Curriculum and Teaching*, 11(8), 467–477. <https://doi.org/10.5430/jct.v11n8p467>
21. NATO Standardization Office. (2014). *STANAG 6001 Language Proficiency Levels* (Edition 5 / ATrainP-5 Edition A).
22. Суслов, В. В. (2024). Готовність майбутніх офіцерів Збройних Сил України до міжнародної комунікації: сутність і структура. *Педагогічна Академія: наукові записки*, (13), 136–144. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15286432>
23. Fosnot, C. T. (Ed.). (2013). *Constructivism: Theory, perspectives, and practice* (2nd ed.). Teachers College Press.
24. Slavin, R. E. (2014). *Educational psychology: Theory and practice* (10th ed.). Pearson Education.
25. Van de Pol, J., Volman, M., & Beishuizen, J. (2010). Scaffolding in teacher–student interaction: A decade of research. *Educational Psychology Review*, 22(3), 271–296. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-010-9127-6>
26. Lahodynskyi, O., Shcherbyna, O., Borynskyi, V., Bloschynskyi, I., & Zinchenko, A. (2023). The ESP teaching and learning at the military academies in Ukraine: Psychological and sociocultural aspects. *Forum for Linguistic Studies*, 5(3), Article 1956. <https://doi.org/10.59400/fls.v5i3.1956>

27. Ellis, R. (2003). *Task-based language learning and teaching*. Oxford University Press.
28. Mayer, R. E. (2020). *Multimedia learning* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781316941355>
29. Freeman, S., Eddy, S. L., McDonough, M., Smith, M. K., Okoroafor, N., Jordt, H., & Wenderoth, M. P. (2014). Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(23), 8410–8415. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1319030111>
30. Czarnecki, J. E. (2020, 8 вересня). *Transforming Athena: Educating military officers during an era of great change through experiential learning*. The Strategy Bridge. <https://thestrategybridge.org/the-bridge/2020/9/8/transforming-athena-educating-military-officers-during-an-era-of-great-change-through-experiential-learning>
31. Havis, L. R. (2020). Active learning strategies for promoting intercultural competence development in students. In J. Keengwe (Ed.), *Developing and supporting multiculturalism and leadership development: International perspectives on humanizing higher education* (pp. 127–144). Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2055-364120200000030011>
32. Chernikova, O., Heitzmann, N., Stadler, M., Holzberger, D., Seidel, T., & Fischer, F. (2020). Simulation-based learning in higher education: A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 90(4), 499–541. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654320933544>
33. Sweller, J., van Merriënboer, J. J. G., & Paas, F. (2019). Cognitive architecture and instructional design: 20 years later. *Educational Psychology Review*, 31(2), 261–292. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-019-09465-5>
34. Alkasem, A., & Mohamed, Y. (2025). The impact of active learning strategies on education and learning achievements. *Ijaz Arabi Journal of Arabic Learning*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.18860/ijazarabi.v8i1.27304>